

Pharmacoeconomic analysis of bromhexine for prophylactic of influenza A and B

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Abstract

The aim of the present analysis is to assess the cost-effectiveness of influenza A and B prophylaxis with bromhexine, used off-label, for the purposes of the healthcare system in Bulgaria.

Cost-effectiveness and cost-benefit analyses were performed from the payer and society perspectives. The compared alternatives are bromhexine and medicines with prophylactic indications according to national regulation (amantadine, rimantadine, zanamivir, and vaccines). Direct medical costs were calculated using official prices and tariffs. Indirect costs were calculated as productivity losses.

The cost of bromhexine prophylaxis is the lowest, at 4.83 Euro per patient, and total medical costs are 1054.56 Euro per 100 patients. In the cost-effectiveness analysis, bromhexine prophylaxis is dominant, with an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) of –3236.72. Net benefits are higher with bromhexine (91989.45 Euro) for 100 people prophylactically treated, with a benefit-to-cost ratio of 33.05.

Bromhexine is a cost-effective alternative when used off-label for the prophylaxis of influenza A and B, in comparison with prophylactic alternatives recommended in the Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline. It also increases net benefits to society.

Keywords

bromhexine, cost-benefit analysis, cost-effectiveness, influenza A and B

Introduction

Globally, 1 billion people are expected to become ill with seasonal influenza each year, with a subsequent 3–5 million cases of complications and 290,000 to 650,000 deaths (WHO 2025). In the United States (US), the annual number of hospitalizations is estimated to be between 200,000 and 400,000, accompanied by approximately 45,000 deaths (13.5 per 100,000 people) (Rothberg et al. 2008; CDC 2025). According to Eurostat data, in 2021 the mortality rate from influenza was 0.07 per 100,000, based on 358 registered deaths (Eurostat 2024).

According to data from the National Centre for Infectious and Parasitic Diseases, in Bulgaria, in 2023, a total of 134,335 cases of influenza and acute respiratory infections (ARI) were registered (incidence 3,614.79 per 10,000 people). For comparison, in 2022 a total of 124,623 cases of influenza and ARI were registered (incidence 3,291.20 per 10,000 people). Mortality varies

widely—between 0.69 per 100,000 in low-risk groups and 2.84 per 100,000 in high-risk groups—which in absolute numbers corresponds to between 9 and 28 people in the population (NCIPD 2023). In Bulgaria, the number of newly diagnosed cases confirms the main risk groups, such as children under 5 years of age and adults over 64 years of age with underlying chronic diseases.

Although low, the probability of hospitalization due to influenza complications (1.6%) is influenced by underlying risk factors (Near et al. 2022). Regardless of age, people with high-risk conditions have higher rates of hospitalization and mortality. The most affected risk group includes older individuals aged 45–64 years with concomitant lung disease, with an estimated 20% of all hospitalizations occurring in patients with underlying lung disease (Irwin et al. 2022). Next are immunocompromised patients with malignancy (OR = 3.7, 270% higher probability of hospitalization), chronic heart disease (OR = 3.2, 220% higher probability of hospitalization), and diabetes (OR = 2.2, 120% higher probability of hospitalization). These data determine the importance of prevention and treatment in older, polymorbid patients.

Influenza viruses are characterized by high variability, which is why immunity after illness or vaccination is not effective for a long period of time. This requires active prophylaxis before the start of each flu season. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and the World Health Organization (WHO) recommend annual active immunization for everyone over 6 months of age (WHO 2025; CDC 2025). The European Commission (EC) has set a goal of achieving 75% vaccination coverage among people over 65 years of age by 2026.

In Bulgaria, it is recommended to immunize adults over 65 years of age before the start of the flu season (MoH 2005). This vaccination is paid for by the state budget and provided through general practitioners (GPs). Despite this policy, the Institute for Market Economy reported that in 2024 only 340,000 people were vaccinated against influenza, which corresponds to approximately 26% of the population above 64 years of age (Institute for Market Economy 2025).

Modern medicine includes attenuated live vaccines for aerosol intranasal administration, as well as inactivated vaccines containing surface antigens of current circulating influenza strains (Mak et al. 2014).

In addition to prophylaxis through vaccination, several medications are indicated for influenza prophylaxis, namely amantadine, rimantadine, zanamivir, and oseltamivir (NCPRMP 2023).

The aim of prevention is not only to avoid the spread of influenza viruses but also to reduce the use of health resources. The use of health resources among infected individuals varies, being highest among children (Loughlin 2003), and includes visits to the GP in 93–98% of

episodes; visits to the emergency department in 6–12% of episodes; multiple visits (three or more) for complications—48% (0–4 years) and 31% (5–14 years) vs. 7% and 5% without complications; antibiotic use for complications—61% (0–4 years) and 63% (5–14 years), compared with 23% and 27% without complications—highlighting potential overuse in the absence of proven bacterial infection; and more frequent clinical procedures for complications, including blood tests (up to 18–20%) and chest X-rays (up to 8–10%).

The main share of the economic burden on health systems worldwide is due to hospitalizations. In the United States and Australia, hospitalizations account for 73–75% of direct costs, equivalent to \$2.3 billion out of \$3.2 billion (de Courville 2022). For the European Union, economic costs are estimated to be between €6 and €14 billion (Preaud 2014). The lowest hospitalization costs are estimated in Germany (€2033 per patient per year) and the highest in Belgium (€6827 per patient per year) (Scholz 2014; Crott 2019). Detailed information on the frequency of hospitalizations and the type of complications is not available for Bulgaria.

In addition to the healthcare system, costs are also generated in society due to absenteeism, reduced productivity, and premature mortality. Indirect costs at the patient level due to absenteeism because of influenza have been estimated at €93 per patient in France (Silva et al. 2014) and €424 in Germany (Ehlken et al. 2015). In Central and Eastern Europe, the estimated cost of influenza-related complications shows the highest volume of healthcare activities and costs in Poland (€822,223 per year) and the lowest in Romania (€35,483 per year) (Kovac 2014). Bulgaria is not included in this estimate.

The cost of influenza prophylaxis and the cost-effectiveness of different alternatives have not been studied in Bulgaria, which motivated the present study.

The aim of the present study is to assess the cost-effectiveness of influenza A and B prophylaxis with bromhexine, used off-label, for the purposes of the healthcare system in Bulgaria.

Materials and methods

Cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) and cost-benefit analysis (CBA) were employed for the purposes of this study.

Perspective of the analysis—payer (National Health Insurance Fund 2023) and society.

Time horizon—1 flu season (usually 3–6 months).

Compared alternatives—bromhexine versus medicinal products included in the National Pharmacotherapeutic Guideline and/or the positive drug list (NCPRMP 2025). Prophylaxis of influenza A and B should be included as an indication in the Summary of Product Characteristics (Table 1).

Table 1. Compared alternatives.

INN	Prophylactic regime	Treatment regime	Indications for reimbursement
Amantadine (influenza A virus)	10–42 days (6 weeks), dose of 2 × 100 mg (12–65 years of age); 100 mg (children 5–9 years and above 65 years)	4–5 days, daily dose of 2 × 100 mg (12–65 years); 100 mg (children 5–9 years and above 65 years)	According to SmPC
Rimantadine (influenza A virus)	2 weeks—adults and children over 10 years of age: two tablets (100 mg) twice daily. Patients over 65 years of age and patients at high risk of complications: 100 mg once a day	5 days according to the scheme: adults and children over 14 years—1 st day: 3 × 2 tablets (100 mg) daily or 6 tablets (300 mg) at a time; 2 nd and 3 rd day: 2 × 2 tablets (100 mg) daily; 4 th and 5 th day: 2 × 100 mg daily. Over 64 years: 2 × 100 mg daily. Children 7–11 years: 2 × 50 mg daily; from 11 to 14 years: 3 × 50 mg daily.	Not reimbursed. Only marketed
Zanamivir	10–28 days, 1 × 2 inhalations	5 days, inhalation for adults and children aged 5 years and over; 2 × 2 inhalations (20 mg).	For the treatment of influenza type A and type B in adults and children (≥5 years); prevention of influenza; post-exposure prophylaxis of influenza type A and type B after contact with a clinically diagnosed case in the family. In exceptional cases, it can be used for seasonal prophylaxis of influenza type A and type B during an epidemic in the community.
Oseltamivir	Single daily dose once a day for 10 days	Available in the form of a powder for the preparation of a suspension with a concentration of 6 mg/mL for administration to infants and children at a dose of 2–3 mg/kg per dose, 2 × daily for 5 days.	Treatment of influenza in adults and children, including infants. Post-exposure prophylaxis in individuals 1 year of age or older. In emergency situations (e.g., mismatch between circulating and vaccine virus strains and pandemic situations), seasonal prophylaxis may be considered in individuals 1 year of age or older; it is indicated for post-exposure prophylaxis of influenza in infants less than 1 year of age during an influenza pandemic outbreak.
Bromhexine	2 × 1 tablet, 3 weeks before the flu season	There are no therapeutic indications for influenza A and B, except for symptomatic treatment of lung diseases characterized by productive cough and difficult-to-clear hyperviscous bronchial secretions: tracheobronchitis, including spastic bronchitis, pneumonia, bronchiectasis, COPD, pulmonary tuberculosis, and pneumoconiosis. Bromhexine is explored off-label for prophylactic indication.	Prescribed once for a therapeutic course for the treatment or prevention of complications from U07.1 (COVID-19—confirmed by laboratory tests) for conditions with ICD codes J12.8, J12.9, J15.8, J15.9, J20.8, J20.9, and J22 (other viral pneumonia, other bacterial pneumonia, acute bronchitis, and acute lower respiratory tract infection).
Trivalent influenza vaccine / Quadrivalent influenza vaccine (split virion, inactivated)	One injection before the flu season		Prevention of influenza disease caused by two subtypes of influenza A virus and influenza B virus contained in the vaccine for active immunization of adults, including pregnant women, and children from 6 months of age and older; passive protection of infants from birth to less than 6 months of age after vaccination of pregnant women.

Sources of data for cost calculation

Direct medical and indirect costs are included. Direct medical costs are for prophylaxis, treatment of the viral infection, and hospitalizations.

Prophylaxis costs are calculated based on the recommended prophylactic regimens in Table 1. Drug prices are taken from the PDL (updated 2 September 2025) at a reference value for a defined daily dose (DDD) (NCPRMP 2025). For non-reimbursed medicines, ceiling retail prices at the pharmacy level were used.

The costs of treating a viral infection are calculated according to the recommendations of the Pharmacotherapeutic Guideline and include costs for analgesics and antipyretics, antivirals, and immunostimulants. For patients without complications, one examination by a general practitioner (GP) is included, and for those with complications, an examination by a specialist is included

according to the tariffs of the National Framework Contract (NFC) 2023–2025 (NHIF 2023). The costs of hospitalizations for complications of influenza were taken from the National Health Insurance Fund as the cost of clinical pathway (CP) 104 “Diagnosis and treatment of contagious viral and bacterial diseases—acute, with complications” (NHIF 2023).

Indirect costs were calculated using the human capital method. For the duration of the acute infection, 3 days of absence from work were assumed based on literature data, and for complications with hospitalizations, 3 days of hospital stay were assumed, which is the minimum recommended stay according to the clinical pathway. Days out of work due to influenza are multiplied by the average daily income (55.33 Euro) of Bulgarians, according to data for the average salary (1161.89 Euro) (NSI 2024). The formula for calculation of the indirect costs is the following:

$$\text{Indirect cost} = (\text{N days out of work due to sick leave} + \text{N days out of work due to hospitalization}) \times \text{average daily income}$$

Sources of data for outcomes measurement

Effectiveness of the compared alternatives was measured through the number of protected people per 100. As protected people were considered those who were expected not to become sick from influenza. Data for the protective effectiveness as the percentage of protected people were taken from the Pharmacotherapeutic Guideline and from published studies, mainly meta-analyses and systematic reviews (Table 5). The results for the effectiveness of bromhexine are taken from the study by Mitev et al. and the study by Marinov et al. 2025.

During CEA and CBA, the highest reported values of protected people per 100 were used.

Cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) and cost-benefit analysis (CBA)

For the purposes of the cost-effectiveness method, the number of cases of influenza A or B avoided with prophylaxis using the selected alternatives was adopted as an outcome measure. Only the cost of prophylactic dosage regimens was used as the cost measure in the CEA.

Net benefit = (avoided costs when on prophylactic (avoided hospitalisation cost + avoided treatment cost when ill) per 100 – (Cost of prophylactic (Cost of prophylactic dosage regime + cost of ambulatory and hospital therapy when ill) per 100)

Benefit to cost ratio = Avoided cost per 100 / Cost of prophylactic per 100

The same types of costs—for prophylaxis, hospitalizations, and ambulatory therapy—were considered for both calculations for the purposes of the CBA.

Sensitivity analyses

Sensitivity analyses were performed to test the robustness of the results separately for the CEA and CBA.

For the CEA, during deterministic sensitivity analysis, costs and results varied within a $\pm 10\%$ interval. Probabilistic sensitivity analysis was performed with 1000 Monte Carlo ICER simulations around the average cost, varied by $\pm 15\%$, and average results, varied by $\pm 10\%$. A cost-effectiveness probability curve was also built to explore the willingness-to-pay threshold for prophylaxis.

For the CBA, during deterministic analysis, the costs and benefits used for calculation of the net benefit ratio

The cost-effectiveness ratio (CER) and incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) were calculated for all compared alternatives during the CEA, using the following formulas:

$$\text{CER} = \text{Cost of prophylactic} / \text{Nof avoided cases}$$

$$\text{ICER} = \Delta \text{Cost} / \Delta \text{Effectiveness}$$

For the purposes of the cost-benefit method, the saved direct medical costs and indirect costs due to the absence of disease and work absenteeism during prophylaxis with the alternatives were taken as outcome measures. In addition to the cost of prophylaxis, the cost of ambulatory therapy when sick for 3 days, the cost of hospitalizations multiplied by the probability of 1.6% for every person expected to develop influenza, one medical examination by a GP for ambulatory-treated sick people, and two examinations for those who were hospitalized were included.

Net benefit and benefit-to-cost ratios were calculated for all compared alternatives during the CBA using the following formulas.

and benefit-to-cost ratio were varied consecutively by $\pm 30\%$ and $\pm 50\%$.

Results

Results from the cost analysis

Drug therapy costs are highest with zanamivir and lowest with bromhexine (Table 2). Prophylaxis with bromhexine has a cost that is twice as low as prophylaxis with the other alternatives and nearly 40 times lower than that with zanamivir.

The cost for 3 days of drug therapy in case of illness is 14.53 Euro (Table 3). These are minimal costs, as patients usually purchase final packages that are for longer therapy, and only the costs for 3 days were taken into account.

Table 2. Cost for prophylactic.

INN	Prophylactic dosage regime	Unit price in PDL	Cost for prophylactic
Amantadine (influenza A virus)	10–42 days (6 weeks) in a daily dose of 2×100 mg (12–65 years of age); 100 mg (children 5–9 years and above 65 years).	0.09	7.72
Rimantadine (influenza A virus)	2 weeks—adults and children over 10 years of age; 2 tablets (100 mg) twice daily.	0.41	11.40
Zanamivir	10–28 days, two inhalations once	3.40	190.48
Oseltamivir	Single dose once daily for 10 days	1.78	17.77
Bromhexine (off-label)	2×1 tablet, 3 weeks at the beginning of the season (subject of the study).	0.11	4.83
Trivalent influenza vaccine	1 amp before the season	10.04	10.04
Quadrivalent influenza vaccine	1 amp before the season	10.04	10.04

Table 3. Cost for 3 days of medicine therapy in case of flu infection.

Treatment cost	Treatment regime	Unit cost	Total
Paracetamol 500 mg	3 days, three times per day	0.31	2.76
Oseltamivir	75 mg per day for 3 days	1.78	5.33
Isoprinosine 500 mg	3 g per day for 3 days	0.36	6.44

In addition to drug costs, the NHIF also has costs for examinations at GPs, which are generated by all patients; costs for examinations at GPs and specialists for high-risk patients (50 Euro); and hospitalization costs for patients who have been admitted to a medical facility (clinical pathway 104–849.44 Euro) (Table 4).

Table 4. Medical costs.

Medical costs	Unit cost according to the National framework contract	N used during influence	Total per patient
GP examination	25	1.00	25.00
Specialists' examination	25	1.00	25.00
Hospitalization	849.44	1.00	849.44
Daily income	55.33	1 day	55.33

The indirect costs, due to a 3-day absence from work, generated by each patient who was not admitted to the hospital are 166 Euro, and for those admitted to the hospital, they are for 6 days and are 332 Euro.

Results from cost-effectiveness analysis

Due to the variability of viruses, imprecise predictions of expected strains, and different characteristics of human infection risk, the protective efficacy of vaccines and medicines varies (Table 5).

When conducting prophylaxis with bromhexine, the number of people who did not report influenza (10.6%) was assumed to be a lack of efficacy.

Table 6 presents the ICER based on the effectiveness and cost of prophylactic data.

Table 5. Avoided infection cases for compared alternatives.

INN	Avoided infections (%)
Vaccines (ECDC 2017)	56%–61%
Amantadine (influenza virus A) (Jeferson et al. 2006)	41%–61.1%
Rimantadine (influenza virus A) (Jeferson et al. 2006)	41%–72%
Zanamivir (Zanamivir SPC 2025)	68%–83%
Oseltamivir (Welliver 2001)	84%–89%
Bromhexine (Mitev et al. 2025; Marinov et al. 2025)	80%–89.4%

Bromhexine, due to the highest number of cases avoided, is the most effective alternative. It is also the alternative with the lowest costs for protection, which is why it is the most cost-effective alternative. For each person prophylactically treated with bromhexine, 3236.72 Euro will be avoided. These are costs for prophylaxis only. The remaining medicines are arranged in sequence: rimantadine, amantadine, oseltamivir, and vaccines. Zanamivir is the least cost-effective alternative and should not be used for prophylaxis of influenza A and B.

In the deterministic sensitivity analysis, the costs of oseltamivir and the effectiveness of zanamivir and oseltamivir most significantly affect the cost-effectiveness of influenza A and B prophylaxis (Fig. 1).

The incremental ratio varies between 14000 Euro and –16000 Euro, respectively, when changing the cost of oseltamivir (Fig. 1). With all variations in costs and results, bromhexine remains the most cost-effective alternative, and ICER values remain stable and low. Even in the prevailing part of the simulations, the ICER is negative, meaning that bromhexine is a dominant alternative.

During the probabilistic sensitivity analysis comparing oseltamivir vs. bromhexine, the ICER remains negative, pointing out that bromhexine is a dominant prophylactic strategy, costing less and providing high benefits (Fig. 2).

The dominant position of bromhexine explains the 100% willingness-to-pay threshold for prophylaxis with bromhexine (Fig. 3).

Figure 1. Deterministic sensitivity analysis for ICER changes during CEA.

Table 6. Cost-effectiveness analysis.

INN	Cost of prophylactic dosage regime per 100 people	Results per 100 people (protected persons per 100)	Δ Cost	Δ Results	ICER
Vaccines	1004.09	61	1004.09	61	16.46
Amantadine (influenza virus A)	772.22	61.1	-231.87	0.10	-2318.69
Rimantadine (influenza virus A)	1139.94	72	367.72	10.90	33.74
Zanamivir	19048.01	83	17908.07	11.00	1628.01
Oseltamivir	1777.32	89	-17270.68	6.00	-2878.45
Bromhexine	482.64	89.4	-1294.69	0.40	-3236.72
Second ordering					
Amantadine (influenza virus A)	772.22	61.10	1512.00	61.00	24.79
Rimantadine (influenza virus A)	1139.94	72.00	367.72	10.90	33.74
Oseltamivir	1777.32	89.00	637.39	17.00	37.49
Bromhexine	482.64	89.40	-1294.69	0.40	-3236.72
Third ordering					
Rimantadine (influenza virus A)	1139.94	72.00	1139.94	72.00	15.83
Oseltamivir	1777.32	89.00	637.39	17.00	37.49
Bromhexine	482.64	89.40	-1294.69	0.40	-3236.72

Figure 3. Willingness-to-pay threshold for bromhexine vs. oseltamivir.

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA)

Benefits for the purposes of the CBA were calculated as avoided costs from people who were vaccinated and did not get sick from influenza. Avoided cases of infection were taken from the studies shown in Table 5, but the

highest effectiveness values were used. Robustness was tested during sensitivity analysis.

Most studies report a reduction in hospital stays because of influenza prevention or treatment with antiviral products, and only one study reported a 30% reduction in the number of hospitalizations with oseltamivir treatment

(Jefferson et al. 2006; ECDC 2017). Near et al. (2022) reported a 1.6% probability of hospitalization due to complications of influenza, which differs among risk groups, but for the purposes of this study, it was assumed that 1.6 out of 100 patients will be hospitalized for all alternatives.

All calculations are presented per 100 people.

Due to the different prophylactic effectiveness of the compared alternatives, the number of avoided hospitalizations will be different, as well as the costs for them (Table 7).

The highest costs for hospitalizations per 100 people who received prophylaxis with the compared alternatives are for vaccinated patients, followed by those who took amantadine, rimantadine, and zanamivir. The lowest costs for hospitalizations are for patients who took bromhexine (144.07 Euro) (Table 7).

Indirect costs due to absence from work are twice as high as direct medical costs, which once again emphasizes the importance of prevention of acute infectious diseases. These usually generate high indirect costs for the entire economy (Table 7).

Benefits as avoided costs are generated by people who took prophylaxis with any of the alternative medicines and did not get sick from influenza. These benefits arise from individuals who were not hospitalized, did not visit

GPs or specialists, did not take medicines when sick, and did not take sick leave (Table 8). Avoided medical costs are five times higher than the indirect avoided costs. This difference is generated mainly from avoided hospitalizations due to prophylaxis. It is also evident that avoided costs are higher for people using bromhexine due to its higher prophylactic effectiveness.

The proportion between paid and avoided costs for different alternatives is presented in Fig. 4.

As evident from Fig. 4, the avoided costs significantly overcome paid costs for prophylaxis with all of the compared alternatives, but they are higher for bromhexine and oseltamivir.

Calculating different net benefit relations, it can be seen that the highest net benefits are observed when prophylaxis is performed with bromhexine (92 thousand for 100 people). For every Euro invested in prophylaxis with bromhexine, society receives 33 Euro in return (Table 9).

Sensitivity analyses for CBA

The sensitivity analysis for net benefits shows that changes in the cost of bromhexine influence net benefits more than changes in effectiveness. Nevertheless, the price of bromhexine is so low that even if it is increased by 50%, net benefits still prevail over those of other medicines (Fig. 5).

Table 7. Types of costs related to prophylactic per 100 people.

	Cost for prophylactic per 100	Cost of hospitalization	Cost of home treatment	Cost for examinations	Cost for examinations for hospitalized	total medical cost for 100 prophylactics	Indirect cost	Indirect cost for hospitalized	Total indirect	Total cost—medical and indirect
Vaccines	1004	530.05	566.67	975	31.2	3106.92	6473.61	207.16	6680.77	9787.69
Amantadine	772	528.69	565.22	972.5	31.12	2869.53	6457.01	206.62	6663.64	9533.17
Rimantadine	1140	380.55	406.84	700	22.4	2649.79	4647.72	148.73	4796.45	7446.24
Zanamivir	19048	231.05	247.01	425	13.6	19964.66	2821.83	90.29	2912.13	22876.79
Oseltamivir	1777	149.50	159.83	275	8.8	2370.13	1825.89	58.43	1884.32	4254.45
Bromhexine	483	144.07	154.02	265	8.48	1054.56	1759.49	56.30	1815.79	2870.35

Table 8. Benefits as avoided costs per 100.

	Avoided cases of prophylactic	Avoided hospitalizations	Avoided cost of hospitalization	Avoided cost for examination	Avoided cost for examinations in case of hospitalization	Avoided cost of home treatment	Total avoided medical cost	Avoided indirect cost	Avoided indirect cost for hospitalized	Total avoided indirect	Total avoided cost (medical and indirect)
Vaccines	61	0.976	51815.84	1525	48.8	886.33	54275.97	10125.39	324.01	10449.40	64725.37
Amantadine	61.1	0.9776	51900.78	1527.5	48.88	887.78	54364.95	10141.99	324.54	10466.53	64831.48
Rimantadine	72	1.152	61159.68	1800	57.6	1046.16	64063.44	11951.28	382.44	12333.72	76397.16
Zanamivir	83	1.328	70503.52	2075	66.4	1205.99	73850.91	13777.17	440.87	14218.04	88068.95
Oseltamivir	89	1.424	75600.16	2225	71.2	1293.17	79189.53	14773.11	472.74	15245.85	94435.38
Bromhexine	89.4	1.4304	75939.94	2235	71.52	1298.98	79545.44	14839.51	474.86	15314.37	94859.81

Table 9. Cost-benefit analysis.

	Net benefit for medical costs	Net benefit for indirect cost	Net benefit for total cost (medical + indirect)	Benefit-to-cost for medical costs	Benefit-to-cost for indirect costs	Benefit-to-cost for all alternatives
Vaccines	51169.05	3768.64	54937.69	17.47	1.56	6.61
Amantadine	51495.42	3802.90	55298.32	18.95	1.57	6.80
Rimantadine	61413.65	7537.27	68950.92	24.18	2.57	10.26
Zanamivir	53886.25	11305.91	65192.16	3.70	4.88	3.85
Oseltamivir	76819.40	13361.53	90180.93	33.41	8.09	22.20
Bromhexine	78490.87	13498.57	91989.45	75.43	8.43	33.05

Figure 4. Proportion between paid and avoided costs.

Figure 5. Sensitivity analysis for net benefits.

The sensitivity analysis for the cost-benefit ratio shows that variations in the benefits and costs of bromhexine within $\pm 50\%$ are more influential than variations within $\pm 30\%$. Despite this, the benefit-to-cost ratio is always positive and above 60 Euro for all variations (Fig. 6).

Discussion

In this study, we attempt to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of using bromhexine off-label for influenza prophylaxis in Bulgaria. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first such study in the country and worldwide. Bromhexine is an OTC medicine with well-established use, recommended as a mucolytic in cases of upper respiratory tract infections. Bromhexine is associated with favorable improvements in mucus clearance and is indicated in various respiratory disorders. It is well tolerated, and side effects are mild.

During COVID-19, bromhexine was reconsidered for prophylaxis and compared with the standard of care for reducing viral load (Depfenhart et al. 2020; Villa Mendez et al. 2022; Tolouian et al. 2022; Bahadoram et al. 2022; Walther et al. 2020; Bentett 2024; Mitev et al. 2025b; Mondeshki et al. 2025). The same mechanism of action is described for prophylaxis of influenza A and B (Mitev et al. 2025a).

The CEA and CBA in this study are based on effectiveness data from the studies by Mitev et al. (2025) and Walther et al. (2020). The costs are those paid by the National Health Insurance Fund and society. Several regulatory papers at the European level strengthen the opportunity for scientific teams to organize and perform clinical trials with already known medicines to fulfill unmet medical needs or in cases of medical emergencies (EMA and HMA 2025; EC 2014; EC 2020; EMA 2025). Economic evaluation is part of these efforts to explore whether society can afford this therapy.

Figure 6. Sensitivity analysis for benefit-to-cost ratio.

Bromhexine is the alternative with the lowest cost and the highest effectiveness. Our results show that bromhexine, as a prophylactic agent used for 3 weeks at doses lower than the treatment dose, is cost-effective for the Bulgarian healthcare system and highly cost-effective for society. The safety of the product additionally increases its cost-effectiveness. Sensitivity analyses confirm these results. Across a wide range of varying costs and outcomes, bromhexine remains cost-effective. It adds benefits to society because it prevents acute forms of infection, decreases the number of people with influenza, and reduces hospitalizations.

The Ministry of Health (Ministry of Health 2005) in Bulgaria has provided free influenza vaccines for people aged 65 years and over since 2019, according to a health program. The goal is to achieve 35% coverage by 2026, but this target has not yet been achieved. Therefore, additional prophylactic options are needed for people who cannot tolerate injections. Bromhexine provides a safe, efficacious, and cost-effective option for these individuals.

Our study has some limitations, as it is the first to explore the cost-effectiveness of off-label use of an OTC product. We acknowledge the off-label use of bromhexine, but we do not consider that it has ethical, clinical, or regulatory implications that would preclude recommending an off-label prophylactic intervention concerning a product authorized for sale in 1963. Products with more than 12 years on the market are considered products with well-established use, and their efficacy and safety are widely documented and proven. In addition, several studies explore the protective effect of bromhexine against COVID-19 infection, as well as one study that explores the protective effect of ambroxol, a bromhexine metabolite.

Effectiveness data were collected from various sources, which might increase the risk of bias. To mitigate this risk, the main results were tested during sensitivity analyses and confirmed. Effectiveness data for bromhexine are taken from two Bulgarian studies by Mitev et al. (2025)

and Marinov et al. (2025). The effectiveness of ambroxol, a metabolite of bromhexine, was explored by Gissen (2000), who concluded that bromhexine can be used for the treatment of viral infections caused by influenza viruses, rhinoviruses, and coronaviruses, as well as for prophylaxis.

A further limitation is that the study assumes a uniform hospitalization risk and fixed productivity losses across all alternatives. This assumption was made because studies reporting hospitalization rates for all alternatives were not available, and a systematic review was used as a source with a higher evidence-based medicine classification. All variations were modeled during sensitivity analyses and are covered by the time-horizon assumptions.

Conclusion

Bromhexine is a cost-effective alternative when used off-label for the prophylaxis of influenza A and B, in comparison with prophylactic alternatives recommended in the Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline. It also increases net benefits to society. There is still a need for stronger clinical evidence before bromhexine can be considered a viable alternative to established influenza prevention strategies, including a regulatory decision to expand its indications.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

VM—patient data collection, design of BRH therapy, clinical data analysis; GP—design of the pharmaco-economic study, cost data collection, methodology, calculations, and data interpretation. Both authors wrote, read, and approved the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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